

Laughing in the Polis: Political Expression Through Stand-Up Comedy in Paris, France

Cambridge Journal of Political
Affairs
Volume 6, Issue 1 (2025): 144-155
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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16632037
cambridgepoliticalaffairs.co.uk

Lorenzo Silvestri, Oskar Steiner & Paul Janson
Sciences Po Paris

Stand-up comedy is booming in Paris, attracting a predominantly young and highly diverse audience, wherein equally heterogeneous performers reflect on their personal experiences regarding topics such as race, gender, and identity. The humorous intersection of personal issues with socio-political themes motivates the following research question: How and why do comedians in Paris claim stand-up comedy as a vehicle of political expression? Drawing on qualitative methods, including participant observations and semi-structured interviews, the study finds that while political expression is an inherent aspect of stand-up comedy, not all comedians recognise the inherently political character of their actions, nor do they stress it as a driving factor. These differences were accompanied by diverging motivations for the performance of stand-up comedy in Paris, ranging from the ubiquitous ambition to make people laugh and have a great time, to educating the audience on a particular subject matter. By situating these findings within an understanding of the political, according to the work of Hannah Arendt and Nina Eliasoph, the research contributes to building an understanding of stand-up comedy as a vehicle of political expression, highlighting its role in contemporary Parisian society.

INTRODUCTION

In March 2022, Netflix released “Standing Up” (“Drôle”), a French series about four aspiring comedians trying to break through in the Parisian stand-up scene. The popularity of this show reflected a wider trend: the steep rise of American-style stand-up comedy clubs in France (Cappelle, 2022). In comparison to the Anglosphere, France’s stand-up comedy scene is young, with many dating its origin to the release of the French television comedy show “Jamel Comedy Club” in 2006 (Logan, 2020).

In its nascent state, French stand-up comedy has attracted a youthful and racially diverse audience, composed largely of those historically marginalised from the more hallowed spheres of France’s traditional performing arts (Cappelle, 2022). Commonly, comedians from marginalised backgrounds use their performance to reflect on their intersectionality. In France, humour has historically been used as an outlet for political expression, with French satirical magazine “Charlie Hebdo” being one of the most prominent and controversial examples (Logan, 2020). French stand-up comedy, however, affords a new stratum of society the means to express their political concerns, often with candour and disregard for convention. Stand-up routines in Parisian comedy clubs regularly address issues such as race, gender or sexual orientation in a personal and direct way, offering a humorous approach that differs from traditional French media. However, empirical work analysing the inherently political content and dimensions of Parisian stand-up comedy in a standardised way is so far lacking.

Humour plays a crucial role in our modern societies and political life. Humour historically formed a versatile instrument for political expression, its significance in social and political discourse commanding a vast body of scholarly inquiry (Gilbert, 1997; Thomas, 2015). Humour possesses the unique ability to highlight deeply troublesome and painful topics, which otherwise would be difficult to discuss, by undermining parts of its own power with its “unserious nature” with which the rhetorical form of jokes is generally considered (Gilbert, 1997). Furthermore, Freud argued for humour’s ability to be used as a social vent that helps society to relieve itself from social, cultural, and political pains (Cohen 1978; Freud, 1990). For its ability to relieve societal pain, humour, especially in the form of stand-up comedy, is often used by minority groups to process and share their experiences of social injustice. The concepts of objectification and otherness are often crucial components in their comedic material, targeted to highlight the comedians’ experienced minority and marginality in the larger social fabric. Self-

deprecation allows for a direct form of social critique, by ridiculing and thus questioning the faulty, which many see as a normal accepted social order and ideals to subscribe to (Gilbert, 1997). Humour thus plays a crucial sociopolitical function, especially for marginalised groups. An analysis of stand-up comedy as a form of political expression and social vent for marginalised groups is therefore essential, especially in the Parisian context of rising social inequalities and marginalised groups facing increasing discrimination (Le Galès and Pierson, 2019; McAvay and Verdugo, 2021).

Scholars have explored the political dimensions of stand-up comedy, particularly within traditions pertaining to Anglo-Saxon cultures. Quirck (2018) dives into the history and development of alternative comedy in the United Kingdom. The author explores how comedians are shaped by and respond to social, political, and economic developments in Britain, proposing an innovative framework for the assessment of stand-up comedy. Similarly, the work of Matthew and Schmitt (2016) explores how stand-up comedians deal with and work with issues such as identity, marginalisation, and taboos. Yet, owing to its relative novelty, scholarly inquiry into the French context remains scarce.

As mentioned above, the French stand-up comedy scene only gained traction with the televised show “Jamel Comedy Club” in 2006 (Béru, 2011). According to Béru, this show wasn’t only a crucial turning point in the history of French comedy because it introduced an entirely new format imported from the United States of America, but also because it addressed “ethnoracial” taboos, such as racism, social discrimination and more generally, life in the *banlieues* using humour, enabling them to make their way into the French public debate for the first time (2011). Such taboos are of an inherently political nature, as they are presented in a communal context of speech and expression, with the aim of affecting and potentially influencing the audience’s opinions or beliefs on a certain topic or issue. The popularity of “Jamel Comedy Club” paved the way for stand-up comedy in France, which became increasingly popular in the years that followed (Béru, 2011). Stand-up comedy never ceased to grow, and indeed, Cappelle observed in the summer of 2022 that Parisian comedy clubs featuring stand-up comedians thrived, drawing predominantly youthful audiences while the more traditional theatres struggled to recapture their pre-lockdown attendance levels in the wake of the COVID-19 disruptions in 2020. Coincidentally, as a social group, French youth are thought to be feeling increasingly disconnected from traditional democratic institutions with a comparatively low election turnout rate (CESE, 2022). Exploring political expression in stand-up comedy permits an understanding of potential alternative avenues for youth political expression in Paris. To do so, an understanding of what the political really means must be developed. Considering the increasing popularity of stand-up comedy in France, and the inherently political nature of taboos, we aim to investigate the role of political expression in French stand-up comedy using a novel theoretical framework based on the seminal conceptualisation of political action by Hannah Arendt, and apolitical expression by Nina Eliasoph. Building on the existing literature on the role of humour, and the political dimension of stand-up comedy, we aim to advance the scholarly discussion to identify and understand the instances of political expression present in Parisian stand-up comedy. This article thus explores youth political engagement in Paris beyond traditional institutions. More precisely, we seek to understand the motivation of comedians to express their political experiences and beliefs through stand-up comedy. This objective was transmuted to the following research question: *how and why do comedians in Paris claim stand-up comedy as a vehicle of political expression?*

In order to answer this research question, we must first clarify our understanding of political expression and make it relevant to the specific relational spaces at hand: Parisian stand-up comedy clubs. Thus, the first section explains our theoretical starting point, delineating an understanding of *the political* that follows from the seminal work of Hannah Arendt, complemented by Nina Eliasoph’s study identifying the political in the apparently *a-political*, allowing us to recognise instances of political engagement and identify instances of politics in stand-up comedy. Subsequently, a description of our ethnographic qualitative method involving participant observations and semi-structured interviews follows, complemented by a brief summary of our main fieldwork results. Then we discuss our findings and link them back to our theoretical understanding of political expression in order to provide an answer to our research question. Finally, a conclusion evaluates and sums up our main findings.

STAND-UP COMEDY AS A VEHICLE OF POLITICAL EXPRESSION

In order to build an empirical understanding of *stand-up comedy as a vehicle of political expression* a few theoretical clarifications are in order. Firstly, we here understand ‘vehicle’ to refer to a means or medium through which agency may be channelled (or performed), where agency refers to conduct(s) that effectively realises an actor’s political intentions (Hay, 2002, pp. 93-95). Furthermore, if attempting to

locate instances of ‘political expression’ in Parisian comedy clubs, a robust conceptualisation of what constitutes ‘political expression’ is in order. While the conventional invocation of ‘politics’ conjures a distinct assemblage of institutions and procedures, we aim to advance a more fundamental conception of the ‘political’, one that may be meaningfully discerned independent of the state, policy or electoral processes.

The work of Hannah Arendt (1998) offers a particularly useful framework in this regard. In “The Human Condition,” Arendt elaborates an understanding of human life that draws a primordial distinction between two modes of being, the *vita contemplativa*, and the *vita activa*. It is in the *vita activa*, Arendt argues, that mankind’s tangible engagement with the world is located, under which three distinct activities may be observed: “labour,” “work,” and “action.” Labour and work, for Arendt, are fundamentally private activities: that is—grounding herself in the Aristotelian tradition—they archetypically occur in the *oikos*, the household, that unit of organisation which is primarily concerned with the sustenance of life. The public realm (*polis*), conversely, is defined by its relationship with action. In the public realm, we are continually confronted with the plurality of humanity. It is here that we are asked to go beyond the activities that sustain our physical form and instead, endeavour to communicate *who* we are (not what we are) through acts of speech and self-expression. The public realm is where we negotiate the irreducible distinctness of human life. Politics then, for Arendt, is fundamentally linked to acts of speech and expression. It is through action—the deliberate assertion and presentation of the self—that we transcend violence and necessity, emerging from the realm of bare, pre-political existence. As she writes: “Aristotle’s definition of man as *zoon politikon* (...) can be fully understood only if one adds his second famous definition of man as a *zoon logon ekhon* (a living being capable of speech)” (1998, pp. 26-27). Importantly, then, politics is not a discrete or tangible thing; it is a relational way of existing in the world and interacting with oneself and one another, founded on speech acts of self-presentation. It is in these relationally-constituted “spaces of appearance” that people may assert their subjectivity, distinguishing themselves from mere objects or organisms. Politics emerges wherever individuals interact in this way, preceding any formal government or public institutions (Arendt, 1998, pp. 198-199).

How, then, given these qualities, might politics as such be observed in the field? Nina Eliasoph, in her 1998 ethnography “Avoiding Politics: How Americans Produce Apathy in Everyday Life,” offers a useful approach. Eliasoph’s study, while focusing primarily on the observation of apolitical expression, is based on an understanding of politics that fundamentally aligns with Arendtian ideas of action. For Eliasoph, politics and the public are produced relationally through speech and active self-expression. That is, “with active, mindful political participation, we weave reality and a place for ourselves within it (...) This is the power to *create the public itself*” (Eliasoph, 1998, p. 17). Crucially though, self-presentation in the presence of others is not a sufficient criterion for political expression. As Arendt notes, it is possible to exist alongside other human beings while simultaneously failing to *act*, to escape the private realm. While attempting to observe the evaporation (or production) of political space, Eliasoph is required to articulate an actionable criterion for political expression that is able to discern between private and public expression in the presence of others. Illustrating the difficulty of such a task, she remarks that “recreation group members took racist and sexist jokes as purely personal statements, but an observer could say, ‘Oh, but they really are talking about politics and just don’t know it’” (Eliasoph, 1998, p. 14). In response, she offers the following as an approach. Rather than imposing a fixed definition of “political,” the aim is to observe how people themselves distinguish between political and non-political issues through interaction. The focus is on “whether or not speakers *ever draw out a topic’s public implications*” (Eliasoph, 1998, p. 15) in recognition of the broader significance of their words—i.e. whether they assume what they say to matter beyond their own perspective. The real concern then, for Eliasoph, is not politics as a topic but as a way of speaking that engages a wider community and expresses public concern.

For Eliasoph, political expression manifests through speech and self-presentation, wherein individuals seek not only to assert the singularity of their subjectivity but to render it meaningful by recognising its inherently relational nature. In weaving a web of connections between subjects, political expression does not merely articulate individual perspectives; it actively forges the public sphere itself, cultivating the very conditions that make further political expression possible. Thus, we argue that political expression can accordingly be interpreted as a style of action or particular use of agency that *inserts oneself into the public sphere by working to create it*. In this sense, stand-up comedy, or humour more broadly, functions as a social ventail as well as a medium for advancing thoughts and ideas that are inherently political. The works by Arendt and Eliasoph are thus well suited for the research aim of identifying political expression in Parisian stand-up comedy.

METHODOLOGY AND DATA COLLECTION

Having established the significance of stand-up comedy in Paris, the social function of humour, and the nature of political expression, we must now turn to the central inquiry: how and why Parisian comedians assert stand-up comedy as a vehicle for political expression.

We approached our research from a qualitative perspective. By utilising an ethnographic approach, we were able to fully immerse ourselves into the world of stand-up comedy, allowing for the identification of patterns in comedy shows (see Lareau and Shultz, 1996). Ethnographic studies are primarily rooted in observation but can also be supplemented by interviews. Concretely, the use of participant observations and semi-structured interviews allowed us to develop a deeper understanding of our research topic and the choices made by our research subjects: stand-up comedians. However, due to time and resource constraints, our project did not encompass a fully immersive ethnographic deep dive; it was instead primarily limited to participant observations based on ethnographic methodologies. Additionally, in an effort to triangulate our observational data, a number of interviews with comedians were conducted. To collect comparable data, we had to achieve a minimum level of standardisation across our observations and interviews. Thus, we developed an observation and an interview guideline (Annex 2 and 3).

Our observation guideline provided the appropriate methodological framework to approach the first part of our fieldwork, informing how we selected venues and prepared for participant observations. Firstly, we needed to identify English-language stand-up comedy shows in Paris. These either took place as open mic nights, where essentially anyone would be able to perform based on a “first come, first serve” principle, or with preselected comedians, sometimes focusing on a pre-prepared theme or topic, as chosen by the host. We focused primarily on preselected evenings, as open-mics were mostly attended by amateurs or beginners but also included one observation at an open-mic night. Furthermore, in order to control our English-language observations, we conducted an observation at a French-language stand-up comedy show. This was randomly selected based on availability and convenience. These criteria might be considered arbitrary, but they effectively permitted us to isolate individual shows from the many that take place in Paris each evening.

Secondly, the observation guideline delineated our behaviour at a comedy show as social scientists and as audience members. At small comedy shows, the host usually speaks to the single audience members before the start. Here, we would always be transparent about the reasons why we were at the show: to enjoy the comedy, but also to conduct research on political expression in stand-up comedy. Thirdly, during the show, we would look out for broad topics addressed in the act (e.g., racism, relationships, daily life in Paris, etc.), the identity of the comedians (their gender, age, etc.), the size and composition of the audience, and the crowd’s reactions to the jokes, or rather to the specific topics addressed by the comedians. So as not to disturb the audience and the comedians on stage, we would avoid sitting in the first row, which usually interacts the most with the comedians, and take notes on our phones. We avoided using a notebook in a setting where its use would have stood out and attracted undesired attention.

For the scope of our study, the observations provided us with an understanding of the world of stand-up comedy, which was necessary to immerse ourselves in it and meet comedians. However, the data required to answer our research question is mainly derived from interviews. This necessitated the development of a clear-focused and streamlined interview guideline. Our guideline was structured in clear-cut sections (*introduction*, *establishing connections*, *qualitative dimensions*, and *conclusion*) that guided our interviews and included potential questions to ask in order to gather our data (see Annex 3). Within the section *qualitative dimensions*, we gathered data on the comedian’s understanding of “the political,” their personal relation to society, as well as their motivations to do stand-up. Naturally, the interviews were nourished by prior observations. Hence, we also discussed the ways in which comedians choose topics, develop jokes, and form relationships with the audience. These insights provided further auxiliary data that potentially indicates how comedians utilise stand-up comedy for political expression. We approached a range of comedians for our interviews, usually after a show or through social media. Incidentally, the four comedians who were willing to speak to us had diverging backgrounds, strengthening the overall significance of the interview data we collected. All interviews were conducted in cafés. Below, the most pertinent results from our observations and interviews are detailed. All interviews and observations were conducted in Paris, France over the course of two months, from

October to November 2022 (see Annex 1). Every comedian and host provided oral informed consent to being included in the study.

FIELDWORK RESULTS

In order to contextualise our main findings, we first need to outline our observation results. We conducted six participant observations at different Parisian venues. Although each venue was different, the number of seats available for the audience usually varied between 30 and 40. On some occasions, the room was packed, on others, there were a few vacant seats. The audience was typically an ethnically diverse crowd in their late 20s and early 30s, with approximate gender parity. Only the French observation stood out, as the audience members looked much younger, primarily in their early 20s. All shows comprised the performance of a handful of comedians, performing between three and five minutes, depending on the event, with a host opening and closing the event, and sometimes the host would also introduce each individual comedian. As one of our interviewees later confirmed, the role of the host is essential in measuring the audience and setting the appropriate atmosphere for the night (Interview 1).

The stand-up comedians themselves were much more heterogeneous than the audience, which was diverse, but still majority white. Although most comedians we observed were men (about two-thirds), they usually were of different ethnic backgrounds. The most common topics that were addressed were love and relationships, work-life, living in Paris or the Parisians, as well as discrimination or racism. The jokes were usually based on alleged personal anecdotes, often built through the establishment of a relationship with the audience, for example by starting the performance with a rhetorical question. We noticed a trend that non-white comedians almost always addressed racism or discrimination in their performances. Furthermore, while the theme of love and relationships, including dating, marriage, gender roles and sexuality, was explored by most performers, it was almost exclusively the focus of female comedians, who frequently centred their entire acts around this subject. In contrast, male comedians did not consistently engage with these themes to the same extent.

As the community of stand-up comedy—especially English-language stand-up comedy—in Paris is small, the hosts and some of the recurring comedians recognised us after our first rounds of observations. Although probably not all of those who recognised us remembered our primary intention to conduct social science research, one of the hosts expressed gratitude to us for returning to his show. This made us increasingly feel at ease during our fieldwork, as we did not sense that we were intruding in any way, advancing our immersion into the world of stand-up comedy.

These observations provided us with the necessary insight to conduct our interviews that constituted the second part of our fieldwork, collecting sufficient information to ask precise questions to our interviewees. We interviewed four comedians from different backgrounds, ranging from a French white male who recently got into stand-up comedy (Interview 1), a transgender man (Interview 2), a French/British woman of African descent (Interview 3), to an established African comedian who recently moved to Paris (Interview 4). Below, our most relevant findings are outlined.

Interestingly, all comedians stressed that their jokes and performances stemmed from personal experiences, insisting that without this grounding, no connection with the audience could be formed, and the humour, as a result, would fall flat. Additionally, a lot of research was found to go into the making of a joke, as lying or sharing incorrect information on stage may be detrimental to a comedian's career. The topics they tackled were of significant personal importance to the comedians, who conveyed a strong desire to share these intimate experiences with an audience willing to give their full attention. When directly questioned about the political dimensions of their comedy, each interviewee elucidated a unique perspective on the political dimensions of their work.

Summing up our main findings, we can highlight the importance for comedians to share personal stories with the audience, with whom they build a connection at the start of their performance. Although comedians approach stand-up differently, their performances tend to converge around major topics, such as love and relationships, daily life, or discrimination. Their interpretation of these performances as a form of political expression is not universally held among comedians, who often have ramified understandings of *the political* in stand-up comedy.

DISCUSSION

To answer our research question, below we first discuss *how* comedians in Parisian stand-up comedy utilise their performance as a vehicle of political expression, followed by a discussion on their motivations, in other words, *why* they do so.

How Do Comedians In Paris Claim Stand-Up Comedy as A Vehicle of Political Expression?

With regards to these results then, we find that—given the understanding of political expression borrowed from Arendt and Eliasoph of politics as the relational act of self-presentation “in front of a wider backdrop” (Eliasoph, 1998, p. 15)—essentially all stand-up comedy can be construed as active political expression. This, we find, is often unintentional (but sometimes knowingly tolerated) and a result of the art form’s inherent nature as a bridge between personal and public. Frequently, however, this engagement with the innate political character of stand-up is a conscious and an explicit choice. These instances, where the baseline political character of stand-up is acknowledged and exploited, are indicative of situations in which performers are more immediately aware of the political character of their own personhood.

Our interviews revealed that the nature of stand-up comedy (as understood by comedians) fundamentally requires the connection of personal experience to public interest. While not necessarily seeing this act as ‘political’ themselves, all the comedians we interviewed were actively aware of this process and saw it as central to their work. This mediation of the personal and the public was observed to require two processes that all the comedians we studied framed as central to their act. Namely, the articulation of some personal truth and the subsequent negotiation of this truth vis-à-vis the web of relations constituting ‘the public.’

Firstly, it was consistently emphasised by the comedians we interviewed that they could only joke about what they knew. When discussing what constitutes a successful routine, Interviewee 2 stated that “so many comics want to appeal to, like a big number of people...but no, speak about yourself, speak about your truth and you, you will find your audience” (Interview 2). When speaking on the boundaries of acceptability in comedy, another highlighted: “I will make fun of my own experience with the Jewish people. Certainly, I cannot make fun of [Jewish people as a whole.]” (Interview 3). Importantly, this knowledge could be either researched and factual, or experiential and observational. In both cases, however, the comedians were explicit as to the fact that any routine had to—in some sense of the term—be true; one’s jokes had to correspond to some intimate and personally-derived understanding of reality. “I talk more about things that touch me ... And that touches the people as well—when you talk about something that is dear to you—compared to when you’re talking about something that everyone already knows... It is necessary that the topic is important to me. If I talk about a subject that I don’t care about, the audience won’t care either” (Interview 1).

The second half of the comedic process was constituted by the need to relate this personally held knowledge to the expectations and understandings of the audience. When describing his writing process, Interviewee 1 continued: “it is important that people recognise themselves. Me, for example, I talk about sales, I talk about me being a store clerk, but also the customer in front. So, people can also see themselves in the customer. So, there is not only the store clerk but there are also those who stand opposite to the store clerk. Everyone can recognise himself in one way or another and this is how you unify” (Interview 1). Comedians thus appeared to understand their job as necessitating a self-projection into the minds of the public, to understand how personal knowledge might resonate with the subjectivities of their viewers. As one comedian contended, “I can even see them [the audience] thinking like ‘that’s exactly what I was thinking!’...When you have that commonality within your own life, they love it too. They’re like, ‘Oh yes. He’s like me.’ Or ‘I like them’ or ‘we’re the same.’ All I care about is my feelings and how they relate to others...with comedy you’re talking about issues that, once again, need to be talked about and finding the humour in it, the connection, the similarity and the differences between all of us” (Interview 3). The comedic act fundamentally lies in (successfully) negotiating the alterity of the audience; by creating, out of difference and individuality, a shared reality in which one’s personal voice has a place and is heard. The statement, “the more it is personal, the more it becomes universal.” concisely summarises this point. (Interview 2).

Certain comedians, however, explicitly framed their comedy—driven by this process of connecting the personal to the public—as a political act. The processes we identify as constituting ‘unintentional’ political expression were still present as a baseline, but we observe that what the comedians understood

to be ‘political’ in their comedy generally related to aspects of their personal life that had themselves become politicised. Here, we can see two things. Firstly, the relational character of stand-up remains in the act. The act is still derived from a process of connecting the personal to the public. The difference here is that we begin to see performers acknowledging the political dimensions of this act, in order to consciously play with its implications. Of interest to us is where this sort of recognition might come from; what is it that leads some comedians to disavow the political nature of stand-up and others to embrace it?

Accordingly, we posit that for one’s comedy to be self-identifying as political—given the inherent personalisation of the art form—one must conceive of oneself in political terms. As Interviewee 2, who is transgender (and explicitly described his comedy in political terms) told us, “For me, stand-up has always been going to war ... My whole being, my whole life is political. My existence is political. This is what people say, this is what people need to understand being transgender. We constantly need to justify our existence” (Interview 2). Similarly, Interviewee 3, a Black woman, explicitly highlighted the role her identity plays in building the political dimension of her comedy: “Most of the time, people will not see [politics] the same way. Some comedians I’m talking about will not write [political jokes] the same way because first of all, they’re not Black. Second of all, they’re not a woman. Third of all they’re not me” (Interview 3).

For comedians whose personal identities were marginalised in some way, the self was thus understood as a site of contest. Who they were, their very personhood, was understood to be unavoidably implicated in the public realm. As a result, by understanding the inherent political character of their being, we suggest that these comedians understand their self-expression to be synonymous to political expression in a way that differs from comedians who self-identify with hegemonic groups and norms. To provide a counterexample, one interviewee, a young white French man, actively denied any political dimension to his comedy. Simultaneously however, he enthusiastically emphasised the role his self-identified ‘hypersensitivity’ played in his routines, using much of the same language around visibility and representation—“it is not a subject people often talk about... still, there are many people like that. In Paris there are many, and we are a good few in France as well” (Interview 1). Here, even while explicitly relating some personal identity to a broader collective, hypersensitivity was not understood to be political but instead a personal quirk. The observed differences in how comedians understand their material to be “political” or not, closely parallel Eliasoph’s account of diverging definitions (1998, 14). Political expression emerges not only by intent, but also through audience reception and the context in which the act takes place. Therefore, despite explicitly denying the political dimension of his comedy, the comedian clearly engages with stand-up comedy in the same way as his peers and his performances may, in this way, be interpreted as political. However, his identity, a ciswhite French man, may indeed blind him to the political dimensions of his work, as his social position may give him the privilege of seeing his experiences as *politically neutral*, unlike comedians from marginalised backgrounds, who recognise more readily the political stakes linked to their self-representation. This is in line with recent academic research that found how privileged social groups may lack awareness of political issues that do not affect them directly (Franke, 2023; Yolmo and Basnett, 2024), and underscores the importance of using an intersectional approach in future studies on political expression in stand-up comedy.

In sum, when responding to the ‘how’ dimension of our research question, we suggest that comedians in Paris claim stand-up comedy as a vehicle of political expression in ways that correspond to their own political consciousness. Much as by being irreducibly unique living beings capable of speech, we are all political actors (c.f. Arendt, 1998), we suggest that when this subjectivity is threatened or contested, the public consequences of our existence (and the personal consequences of the public’s existence) render the political relationship between the two more apparent. This process is revealed and reflected in our observations on the presence of both explicit and unintentional political expression in Parisian stand-up comedy.

Why Do Comedians in Paris Claim Stand-Up Comedy as A Vehicle of Political Expression?

Turning to the second component of the research question, the ‘why’ dimension, this section of the discussion focuses on the motivations and objectives of comedians in Paris to engage in stand-up comedy. Particular interest is placed on whether the two diverging understandings of explicit and unintentional political expression also entail a manifestation of different motivations.

Based on the interviews, three common motivations were mentioned by all the comedians to be instrumental to their desire to do stand-up comedy. At the stem of these motivations stood a desire to entertain and to make people laugh. Most interviewees described a previously existing involvement and passion for the performing arts, which in all cases constituted the initial factor drawing them to stand-up comedy. Included in this tendency for entertainment was always the desire to make people laugh, arguably constituting the most fundamental characteristic of stand-up comedy itself. As Interviewee 4 described: “The main goal is to make people laugh.” Consequently, the audience’s laughter is recognised as the deciding factor, determining the success of a performance, with jokes being readjusted and reworked until the desired laughter is achieved.

In light of the previously discussed need for believable jokes to be based on personal experiences and to be relatable, comedians thus often resort to searching for ridiculousness in day-to-day experiences. While this approach outlines a method for achieving the fundamental goal of eliciting laughter, it is simultaneously recognised as a distinct motivation for comedians to engage in stand-up comedy. “I want to show how we [humans] are... [we have] a way of doing things that is funny” (Interview 1). Such topics can span all domains of the human experience, with topics addressed during the observations ranging from gender roles and dating, to work, etc. We see here the role of comedy in assembling a public, in drawing together a shared humanity on the basis of otherwise individualised experiences.

A last motivation for doing stand-up comedy was found to be the desire to vocalise topics that are important to oneself, and that one would normally not find the chance to express. When asked about why he talks about hypersensitivity in his comedy, Interviewee 1 stated: “Because it is not a subject people often talk about (...) and it is something that concerns me (...) and because it makes people laugh.” Furthermore, the very nature of stand-up comedy was found to be beneficial for addressing such otherwise underrepresented topics. Several interviewees credit that standing “behind the shield of it being a joke” (Interview 2) allows them to talk about topics they normally would feel more uncomfortable to talk with their friends about. Additionally, they all recognised the position of power that the comedian is granted through the material and symbolic arrangement of the theatre, installing them as a figure capable of speech and demanding of attention. “I am here in front of you. I have the microphone and you have to listen” (Interview 2). Protected by the shield of humour and the performers’ accepted position of power on stage, stand-up comedians are in the position to scrutinise any aspect of their lived experiences that they deem significant.

These three motivations to do stand-up comedy, highlighting the ridiculousness of daily life, not shying away from largely withheld topics and, most importantly, the desire to make people laugh, were shared by all the interviewed comedians. However, those who explicitly understood their comedy to be political pronounced these objectives alone to be insufficient to them. Instead, their main objective in doing comedy was grounded in education and teaching. “This is my main motivation to do stand-up. It’s really to educate” (Interview 2). Interviewee 2 compared his duty to that of a “lighthouse,” which “puts light on stereotypes, clichés, anything wrong with society,” a logic which ultimately follows the same approach of highlighting the ridiculous in the world, as it is done by all comedians. The crucial difference is that the process in this case does not end with identifying something humorous, but instead is extended to the evaluation of a situation as either right or wrong, followed by the desire to “mobilise” (Interview 3) and to “make the world a better place” (Interview 2). In these two cases, the fundamental characteristics of stand-up comedy—the performer’s position of power and the generally easy-going atmosphere between both parties—are found to play an especially important role in accustoming the audience to the performer’s logic and allowing the “planting of a seed” of those values (Interview 2; Interview 3). The insights from the interviews thus suggest a direct correlation between a strong awareness of one’s own identity, comedy as explicitly political, and the objective to use comedy as a medium to disseminate values that correlate with one’s own political identity.

We equally suggest that this motivation is strengthened by an institutional political culture in France that emphasises the ‘universality’ of its citizens and does not accommodate public discussions of *difference* between political subjectivities, which are deemed, in the republican framework, to risk the promotion of secessionist and identitarian programs (Lefebvre, 2003). With specific regard to questions of race—a form of identity which has no legal recognition or representation in France—stand-up comedy thus offers a unique venue that, while nominally private, allows questions of race and racialised identities to be framed as a matter of public concern. Interviewee 3, a Black woman, explicitly recounted her realisation of this fact and its role in motivating her use of comedy as a vehicle of political expression.

Expressing an initial fear that jokes about race would be poorly received by a French crowd, she explained that: “[Now] I will write my jokes thinking ‘well, this is just for a French-speaking audience’ and not a French *mentality*. Because that used to block me. I used to think ‘ahhh they will not understand... I cannot bring up issues like race,’ and now I’m like ‘oh my fucking god! Not only do I need to...I am good at it!’... [Before,] I thought people would be sensitive maybe... I forgot that they came to laugh ... If the joke is good, fuck it. People laugh, people love it” (Interview 3).

Finally, the last part of the above quotation draws attention to the ambiguous role of humour in conveying political ideas. For Interviewee 3, humour offers an important medium with which to broach potentially taboo ideas. Interestingly, however, the stance of Interviewee 4 directly challenged the use of humour to educate, as he recalls a story where the audience understood one of his jokes in the opposite way as originally intended by him, substantiating his belief that a comedian is never fully able to control how his jokes are being interpreted by the audience. “Some of the audience expect to be educated. But it doesn’t work that way” (Interview 4).

To sum up the discussion on ‘why’ comedians in Paris use stand-up comedy as a vehicle for political expression, a universal drive to entertain and make people laugh was identified amongst all interviewees. In the case of the two comedians with explicitly politicised identities, the desire to entertain was dwarfed by the will to educate the audience about matters of subjective identity, as strengthened by a lack of available means to discuss questions of identity in French political life. Building on the previous discussion, we suggest that a perceived threat to one’s political subjectivity might motivate the creation of more educational comedic content. Finally, stand-up comedy introduces another layer of ambiguity to the already elusive and subjective realm of political expression. The presence of humour, in conjunction with audience expectations, obscures the true intent of the comedian and audience, by introducing a friction in the communication of ideas, rendering political expression within comedic forms simultaneously potent and indeterminate. This ambiguity can thereby act as both a facilitator of and an obstruction to the expression of political narratives in comedy.

CONCLUSION

Sparked by a desire to investigate the current proliferation of stand-up comedy in Paris, we began our research with the question, “How and why do comedians in Paris claim stand-up comedy as a vehicle of political expression?” Borrowing our understanding of political expression—as a form of self-presentational action that both inserts oneself into and creates the public sphere—from Hannah Arendt and Nina Eliasoph, we discuss literature establishing a link between humour and politics and the stand-up comedy scene in Paris more generally. After describing our methodology and detailing the results of our observations and interviews, we attempt in our discussion to offer an answer to our research question. With regards to the ‘how?’ embedded in our question, we find that political expression in stand-up comedy is almost always present as an unintentional baseline given the nature of the art form itself as a bridge between personal and public, making stand-up comedy inherently political. We also find multiple instances where comedians explicitly identify this political character of their comedy—these tend to correspond to cases where the comedians’ identities themselves are politicised. Finally, with regards to the ‘why?’ we find an array of motives. All comedians we spoke to emphasised the simple desire to entertain and make people laugh, while some specifically emphasised the need to educate the public on a particular topic. These comedians raised the importance of humour as a vehicle for communication, as well as the ‘protected’ position they felt they occupied on stage. Others did not identify as being driven by political considerations at all, even when incorporating political references in their performances. This finding provides auxiliary empirical evidence confirming recent research efforts that individuals from privileged social groups may not recognise the political dimensions in their lived experiences. Nevertheless, if stand-up comedy continues to flourish, it not only serves as entertainment to a young and diverse audience but also as a platform to challenge societal and institutional norms, making it a powerful medium of political expression in the Parisian *polis*.

Finally, it is important to evaluate the limits of the data used to reach our findings, summed up above. First and foremost, the argumentation is based on a limited number of observations and interviews, conducted in a restricted time frame that did not allow for a full ethnographic deep dive. Thus, in a qualitative analysis of political expression in Parisian stand-up comedy, observation bias cannot go unaddressed. Additional interviews and observations during different times of the year and over a longer period are needed to determine if our sample is representative. Additionally, the observations and interviews helped us in triangulating our findings; however, further sources supporting our conclusions

are needed to enshrine them. We must also address that although we critically developed our interview guidelines, it cannot go unsaid that the framing of our questions may have impacted answers. We explicitly addressed the role of politics in stand-up comedy and whether the comedians viewed their comedy as an act of political expression only at the end of the interview. However, our guidelines clearly led us to these questions, steering the conversation in one specific direction. Further research is needed to address these implications, but also to reduce the uncertainty of our findings. Lastly, while we have attempted to sketch the outlines of an explanation, the most interesting finding for us consisted of the fact that—despite engaging in the same fundamental personal-public connective process—certain comedians were more explicitly aware of the political quality of such an act than others. For some, the personal was political, while for others, it consisted narrowly of the sphere of news and government. We believe that additional research operationalising a more thorough investigation of how comedians come to build their own definition(s) of *the political*, with particular attention to the role of identity and intersectionality, would further illuminate our findings.

Lorenzo Silvestri, Oskar Steiner & Paul Janson

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ANNEX 1: LIST OF INTERVIEWS AND OBSERVATIONS

Fieldwork	Date	Location
Interview 1	November 12th, 2022	Paris, France
Interview 2	November 21st, 2022	Paris, France
Interview 3	November 14th, 2022	Paris, France
Interview 4	November 24th, 2022	Paris, France
Observation 1	October 13th, 2022	Paris, France
Observation 2	October 27th, 2022	Paris, France
Observation 3	November 8th, 2022	Paris, France
Observation 4	November 12th, 2022	Paris, France

ANNEX 2: OBSERVATION GUIDELINE

Pre-observation preparation:

- Venue selection: language of performance? Time and date? Any known comedians?
- Be transparent to the host
- Do not sit in the first row so as not to create attention or risk of being accused of copying jokes

Observing performers:

- Identify political themes and topics of performances (e.g., race, gender, social inequality, relationships, daily Parisian life, etc.)
- Performers and their jokes:
 - Performers' demographics (e.g., gender, ethnicity, age)
 - Identity and background and how they are portrayed in the performance
 - How performers draw on personal experiences in their material
 - Identify jokes or segments that directly or indirectly address political issues or themes, such as policies, social struggle, government, or activism. Are they explicitly political or not?
 - Tone of jokes (e.g., satirical, self-deprecating, critical, etc.)
 - Methods used to connect with the audience (e.g., rhetorical questions, anecdotes, etc.)
- Observing the audience:
 - Demographics (e.g., gender, ethnicity, age)
 - Reactions
 - Moments of audience-performer engagement/building connections with performer
- Atmosphere: Overall mood of the venue (light-hearted, tense, etc.)
- Physical space: does it encourage interactions between comedian and audience?

Post-observation reflection:

- Reflect on themes, patterns, and atmosphere
- Note any challenges faced during observation

ANNEX 3: INTERVIEW GUIDELINE

Area of interest	Potential guiding questions
<i>Introduction</i>	<i>Ice-breakers</i>
General questions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevant demographic questions (e.g., age, since when in Paris?) • What got you into stand-up comedy? • Why are you a stand-up comedian? • Developments of stand-up comedy in France/Paris? Especially post Covid • What rhetorical tools do you mobilise in your performances? Do you have any favourites?
<i>Establishing connections</i>	<i>Is there a link between our two objects?</i>
Humour and politics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What topics do you address in your stand-up comedy? Why? Do you think of a specific target audience? • What effect can humour have on political statement/expression? • How is humour helpful to convey political ideas?
Sites of political discourse	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How does a perfect site for stand-up comedy look like?/How do you imagine such a venue? • Do you develop intimacy with the audience? What is your relationship with the audience? • Do you think comedy clubs are appropriate to address political discourse? • How does the way you address this topic in stand-up differ from how you address it in your private life? • Do you only address political subjects within your performances? Why? Do you address politics outside comedy? Any differences?
<i>Qualitative dimension (why? how?)</i>	<i>What is the nature of this link? Why does it exist?</i>
Ideology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Belief • Political ideas • In case they consider their comedy as political: do you feel pressure to address politics in your stand-up comedy?
Identity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Representation, self-presentation, creating a character • Class situation • Gender roles personal experience
Norms and behaviour	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relationships with partner/family/friends • Speech: what can be said and where • Social-wide experiences: work-life, gender roles socially accepted • Reflection on society
Conflict/consensus	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What do you try to achieve with your comedy vis-à-vis the audience? • How much do the reactions by the audience determine your comedy/the topics you address? • Do you see your comedy as mobilising or as a catalyst for any sort of action? • Is this action reconciliatory or conflictual?
General thought	Do you consider your comedy as political?
<i>Conclusion</i>	
General	Demographic questions if relevant, end on a light note, maybe asking where they will perform next